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ESG Rating Divergence and Trade Credit Financing: Unveiling the Hurdles to Corporate Liquidity and Growth

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Abstract

ESG ratings have emerged as a critical determinant in trade credit decision-making, reflecting the growing emphasis on sustainability in corporate finance. This study investigates how ESG rating divergence impacts trade credit financing, focusing on customer concentration as the mediating economic mechanism. The analysis utilizes data from Chinese A-share firms listed on the Shenzhen and Shanghai stock exchanges. Robustness tests, including instrumental variable methods, time grouping analysis, and alternative measures, confirm that ESG rating divergence significantly reduces trade credit financing. Second, ESG rating divergence negatively affects trade credit financing by diminishing customer concentration. Third, the heterogeneity based on active ESG disclosure, high-carbon emissions, absence of Big Four firms, and higher debt costs face a more pronounced negative impact of ESG divergence on trade credit financing. Finally, divergences in the social and environmental pillars of ESG ratings are the primary drivers of reduced trade credit financing

Keywords: Trade credit financing, ESG rating divergence, Customer concentration, corporate growth, cost of debt, ESG disclosure.

1. Introduction

To maintain essential liquidity, firms often rely on trade credit financing. Yang and Birge. (2018) evidenced that trade credit is 1.3 times more prevalent than bank loans. In the 1990s, trade credit financed \$1.5 trillion in assets, surpassing the amount of new equity issued and debt. This trend aligns with the observation that accounts payable consistently represented about 10% of firms' assets (D'Mello and Toscano, 2020; Freeman, 2020). Trade credit enhancement can improve the performance of operations, finance, stock returns, and competitiveness, lessen information problems, and support overall firm development (Hill et al., 2012). Essentially, trade credit affects short-term offers and firms' taking loans. However, trade credit is highly prone to financial crises and monetary shocks due to economic policy uncertainty in terms of taxes, government spending, regulatory and monetary policies (Choi and Kim, 2005). When firms are financially weak or times of uncertainty are high, they restrain their financing to customers through trade credit (Phan et al., 2019).

With the growing prominence of signaling theory that explains that information intent and quality are the most important elements (stiglitz, 2002). The information helps the investors to make decisions and devise their portfolio. Firms now face dual objectives: achieving both monetary and non-monetary goals (Battilana et al., 2022). A key challenge in this perspective is the divergence in ESG ratings, which has become a central issue in evaluating corporate sustainability. Standardized criteria are essential to assess corporate sustainability accurately (Maneenop et al., 2023). However, as signaling theory shows direct relationship between credible sender and resultant action by receivers. It eliminates time constraint showing the signal and action. Berg et al., (2022) highlighted the significant challenges in assessing ESG rating performance. In

practice, this divergence creates problems for stakeholders to evaluate firms and develop biased choices, as different rating agencies often apply varying measures to the same firm (Berg et al., 2022; Aabo and Giorici, 2022; Erhart, 2022).

The present study investigates whether and how divergence in ESG rating influences trade credit financing. Previous literature has overlooked the influence of rating divergence on trade credit financing and its broader impacts on economic and firm performance (Christensen et al., 2022), which presents additional challenges for firms. Past studies concentrate on ESG rating scores as an alternative for ESG disclosure, overlooking the potential influence of rating disagreement on research outcomes. While a few studies have identified drawbacks related to ESG ratings, such as lack of clearness (Widyawati, 2020), vague measures (Cornell, 2021), and size-related biases (Drempetic et al., 2020), many fail to address the consequences of rating divergence (Pacelli et al., 2023; Chatterji et al., 2009; Billio et al., 2021; Halbritter and Dorfleitner, 2015). Some past studies have investigated the causes of disagreement in ESG rating, which stem from variances in measurement, scoring methodologies, and weighting biases (Chatterji et al., 2016; Berg et al., 2022; Dimson et al., 2020; Capizzi et al., 2021), but the area of ESG rating divergence on trade credit financing remains under-researched.

While the prevalent studies acknowledged the significance of ESG rating divergence, they largely overlooked its impact on firms' outcomes and performance (Zhou et al., 2024). Only limited work has explored ESG rating divergence and its effects from signaling theory perspective (Gibson et al., 2021; Serafeim and Yoon, 2023). Trade credit shows a crucial role in serving firms attain their goals, reducing pressure from suppliers, and building stakeholder trust (Wang et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2023). However, it is still unclear how companies can use trade credit financing during a divergence in ESG rating. The existing literature lacks findings and evidence to address this question. Therefore, present research gap stimulates us to investigate the effect of divergence in ESG rating on trade credit through both borrowing and lending lenses, contributing to more profound insights into the understanding of ESG rating divergence on firms' financial and economic outcomes.

This study focuses on Chinese A-share firms for many reasons. First, Chinese firms provide an exclusive context to explore the relationship between ESG rating divergences and trade credit financing. The environmental disclosure practices of Chinese firms differ from those of global firms, particularly U.S. firms, which emphasize shareholder interest and governed by external shareholders. Yoon, (2021) highlighted that in the U.S. market, external governance bodies, such as the government, private banks, shareholders, influence corporate disclosures related to environmental safety based on market demand and shareholder priorities. Second, Chinese non-financial A-share firms face less risk compared to financial firms, encouraging managers to hide poor performance by exaggerating positive disclosures. Third, China's economic reform since 1978 has resulted extensively enhanced state owned firms, influencing economic growth (Naughton, 2017). Currently, the state owns approximately 40% firms, while 60% firms are market-capitalized (Jiang and Kim, 2015). In state-owned enterprises (SOEs), managers face less conflict of interest when disclosing bad news, and information manipulation (Cheng et al., 2015). Therefore, China's distinctive institutional quality framework provides a balanced view between rational decision-process and opportunistic behavior as key drivers of ESG rating divergences and trade credit financing.

To summarize the findings, we have utilized data about Chinese non-financial publically listed firms from 2018-2022. We have documented a statistically significant negative influence of ESG rating divergence on trade credit financing. These findings remain robust after using instrumental variables to mitigate endogeneity concerns. Furthermore, our result remains robust after adjustment of dependent and independent variable's measure. We also explore how ESG rating divergence influences trade credit financing. We document that the divergence of ESG rating reduces trade credit financing through declining customer concentration. Finally, in the heterogeneity analysis, we find that firms classified as having a high carbon emission, high voluntary disclosure, higher cost of debt, and firms not audited by big4 audit firms reduce trade credit financing when divergence in ESG rating increases.

Present study contributes to the literature on ESG rating divergence, trade credit financing, and customer concentration from multiple perspectives. In contrast to prior studies, the present study contributes to the

scope of variables affecting trade credit financing from the perspective of ESG rating divergence. Prior literature often investigates the influence of ESG performance on trade credit (Wang and Yang, 2024; Luo et al., 2023), frequently overlooking divergence in ESG rating and between distinct agencies (Li et al., 2024; Cao et al., 2023). Therefore, addressing this problem is vital to reach unbiased results (Dumrose et al., 2022; He et al., 2023). Hence, this study contributes in the scant literature where firms have to increase ESG disclosure while simultaneously focusing on the divergence arising from voluntary disclosure.

Second, this study further investigates how suppliers and customers consider divergence in ESG rating into their shorter payment period and demand a quicker payment in their framework of decision-making. Zhou and Liu (2023) has mainly focused on only investors' investment perspectives on ESG rating, abandoning both suppliers' and customers' perspectives and choice complexity during ESG divergence. Therefore, this research highlights the need for suppliers and customers to comprehensively consider the methodology and rating standards employed by distinct rating agencies.

Third, the present study expands contribution in trade credit financing literature. How external uncertainty, such as economic policy uncertainty (EPU) (D'Mello and Toscano, 2020) and the COVID-19 pandemic (Fulkerson et al., 2024), reduces trade credit financing. We have identified divergence in ESG rating as another important external factor that can inhibit corporations from enhancing trade credit.

Finally, this study makes contribution in financing decisions by investigating the influence of ESG divergence on trade credit. For example, previous studies have revealed that ESG rating divergence reduces corporate innovation (Li et al., 2024). Furthermore, divergence in ESG ratings also affects capital structure by enhancing the cost of equity capital (Mio et al., 2024), declining stock excess return (Wang et al., 2024), enhancing audit fees (Ling et al., 2024), enhancing risk premium (Gibson et al., 2021), declining analyst forecast quality (Liu et al., 2024), and declining stock price risk (Luo et al., 2023). We expand this literature by investigating the impact of ESG rating divergence on trade credit from the perspective of short-term lending and borrowing between suppliers and customers, a vital corporate financing source.

The remaining paper is structured as follows; Section 2 deliberates the theoretical framework and hypotheses construction. Section 3 outlines the data and methodology. Section 4 shows the findings. Section 5 provides the conclusion. Finally, Sections 6 and 7 address the policy suggestions and limitations of the research, respectively.

2. Conceptual Framework and Hypothetical Development

2.1 Trade Credit financing and ESG rating divergence

Trade credit financing is vital for fostering corporate growth (Tingbani et al., 2024). Trade credit financing is affected by both external and internal variables such as internal control, firm characteristics, management characteristics (Kong et al., 2020), financial environment (Casey and O'Toole, 2014), economic condition (Benmelech et al., 2017), and monetary policy (Fishman and Love, 2003), respectively.

The divergence in ESG rating between several ESG rating agencies may influence the following factors: declining ESG information quality, enhancing cost of information processing, and enhancing information asymmetry. Hence, the theory of information asymmetry (George, 1970; Verrecchia, 2001) highlights that interaction between these factors significantly influences trade credit finance due to divergence in ESG rating. To examine in-depth, let's start with the exploration that dispersion in ESG rating contemplates confusion in the market regarding ESG performance, hence reducing ESG information quality and ESG performance, play a pivotal role in the investors' decision making. However, this enhanced focused conceded to ESG has caused confusion in the market (Yu et al., 2018).

The standards and concepts of ESG are regularly advancing, with different ESG prerequisite widespread in distinct industries and countries. Hence, this dispersion constitute challenges in developing a consistent framework for ESG evaluation. Resultantly, agencies of ESG ratings use distinct sources and methodologies to evaluate a firm's true ESG performance (Christensen et al., 2022; Berg et al., 2022). Suppliers, investors, and customers might perceive disparities between rating agencies as a signal of instability and subjectivity in ESG evaluation (Billio et al., 2021), eroding the reliability of ESG ratings. This skepticism might erode

supplier, and customer trust related to ESG rating, declining value of information and negatively influence trade credit financing.

Additionally, divergence in ESG rating enhances the burden of information processing on customers and suppliers. Suppliers and customers must invest more resources and time into data sources, apprehending the methodologies used by distinct rating agencies. The heightened information processing cost might decrease suppliers' and customers' attention far from ESG rating factors, or they may become cautious about rating before making investment decisions (Dunbar et al., 2023). Consequently, certain suppliers and customers start avoiding ESG ratings, thus decreasing credit extension from the ESG perspective, declining a trade credit's ESG influence, and, resultantly, exerting a statistically negative influence on trade credit financing.

ESG rating divergence may exacerbate information asymmetry (George, 1970; Verrecchia, 2001) regarding a firm's actual ESG performance between internal and external stakeholders, thereby increasing uncertainty of ESG performance for customers and suppliers. As D'Mello and Toscano. (2020) conclude that uncertainty in economic policy enhances cash flow volatility, which in turn enhances default risk. Similarly, Gulen and Ion (2016) also advocate that enhancement in uncertainty reduces capital investment, which negatively influences the financial stability and future cash flows of the firms, consequently lowering the asset available for collateral to raise funds.

Furthermore, Mao et al. (2024) evidenced that divergence in ESG rating enhances the degree of earning management for firms facing higher ESG rating divergence. Similarly, Ling et al. (2024) documented that enhanced operational risk, heightened information asymmetry, and elevated debt cost exerting ESG rating divergence significantly increase audit fees. Furthermore, Li and Lai. (2024) indicate that excessive ESG divergence worsens stock price volatility, but this linkage between divergence and volatility is mitigated when corporate information disclosure compliance improves. Liu et al. (2024) confirm that disagreement in ESG rating reduces the quality of analyst forecast by exacerbating information asymmetry; this leads to significant forecast inaccuracies and divergence. Furthermore, it has also been evidenced that divergence in ESG rating increases idiosyncratic return volatility in China (Liu et al., 2024). Based on these arguments, firms' ability to extend credit time from suppliers and willingness to credit extensions to customers will be reduced. Based on the foregoing consensus, we may present the following hypotheses:

H1: ESG rating divergence negatively affects the trade credit financing.

2.2 Mediating role of customer concentration

The signaling theory explains that the signaler possesses critical insider information that is less known publicly or not readily accessible to stakeholders. This theory suggests that both negative and positive information can be valuable for stakeholders, as it may stem from new insights or past reflections (Kirmani and Rao, 2000). From the perspective of signaling theory, examining the adverse impact of ESG rating divergence and the responsive behavior of customers contributes to the literature by demonstrating how ESG rating divergence hinders trade credit financing through the transmission of poor signals about ESG performance.

Furthermore, signaling theory posits information quality can be helpful for the stakeholders and consumers to consume information about pricing structures, firms' networks, human resources, bilateral contracts, payment terms and reputation of the firms that helps minimize the information asymmetry. By providing clear information on ESG, firms can develop a competitive advantage by nurturing constructive interactions with stakeholders (Cheng et al., 2014). A firm's ESG performance reflects its responsible approach toward society and environmental concerns, indicating its commitment to stakeholders' and customers' interests beyond mere shareholder profits. Engaging in ESG activities enables firms to build or sustain robust relationships with internal and external stakeholders, thereby accruing intangible assets such as reputation, corporate image, brand recognition, and customer loyalty (Li et al., 2021). ESG establishes the customers' trust in firms' decisions on business portfolios (Porter & Kramer, 2006). This trust enables the stakeholders to avail the trade credit financing (Luo et al., 2023). ESG performance improves the trade credit by dropping the facts of lopsidedness, improving operating efficiency, and minimizing operational risk.

In contrast, divergence in ESG ratings inhibits customers from understanding firms' ESG performance, consequently influencing their corporate valuation and buying decisions. Consequently, information transparency plays a vital role in the association between customers' concentration and ESG rating divergence. Without transparency, investment decisions would be affected, and confusion about such decisions would increase (Wang et al., 2023). Consequently, customer concentration would be diverted to rating agencies that disclose information in detail and with reliable measures. By knowing the ESG risks and opportunities, firms empower the customers.

On the contrary, a lack of transparency reduces the customers' response to the firm's investments. In the atmosphere of doubts and uncertainties, customers would sense more risk. Such situations could prompt customers to decrease buying from the specified firm, consequently affecting trade credit financing (Wang et al., 2024). Furthermore, higher customer concentration may enhance the influence of ESG rating divergence. For example, if firm's top customers prioritize sustainability, inconsistent ESG rating may undermines trust and leads to tighter credit terms. Therefore, the higher divergence in ESG rating will increase the uncertainty of ESG and decrease true performance; consequently, top customers will reduce purchasing from the firms. Hence, we may hypothesize that,

H2: ESG rating divergence negatively affects trade credit financing through lowered customer concentration.

3. Methods

3.1 Data source and sample selection

We have utilized a dataset of publicly listed Chinese non-financial firms from 2018 to 2022 as the primary inquiry sample for our study. The dataset initially included 4,034 firms, with 2,375 registered on the SSE and 1,659 on the SZSE. To confirm data quality, we applied stringent screening criteria. First, we removed 273 firms due to missing financial data and non-compliance with accounting standards. Additionally, 307 firms were excluded from special treatment (ST), ST*, and PT conditions that could skew the study's results. We also excluded 125 observations with missing variables. After these adjustments, our final sample consisted of 12,846 firm-year observations across 3,429 companies. To alleviate the effect of outliers, we have winsorized all continuous factors at the 1st and 99th percentiles.

We collected data from several forums. First, ESG rating divergence—including environmental, social, and governance rating divergence was retrieved from the Bloomberg, Refinitive, and CNRDS databases. Second, trade credit finance and customer concentration data were obtained from the China Stock Market and Accounting Research (CSMAR) and CNRDS databases, respectively. Finally, the remaining control variables and other financial data are outsourced from CSMAR.

3.2 Econometric model

This body of research assesses the role of ESG rating divergence on trade credit finance by examining environmental, social, and governance rating divergence. This variable is continuous and takes only positive values. To analyze the data, we employed a panel fixed effects model for regression analysis. The subsequent model was established to explore the association between ESG rating divergence and trade credit finance.

$$TRDCF_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 ESG_RD_{i,t} + \gamma Controls_{i,t} + \lambda_{i,t} + \lambda_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

$$TRDCF_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 E_RD_{i,t} + \gamma Controls_{i,t} + \lambda_{i,t} + \lambda_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (2)$$

$$TRDCF_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 S_RD_{i,t} + \gamma Controls_{i,t} + \lambda_{i,t} + \lambda_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (3)$$

$$TRDCF_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 G_RD_{i,t} + \gamma Controls_{i,t} + \lambda_{i,t} + \lambda_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (4)$$

In the model above (1), i stands for the firm, and t for the year. $TRDCF_{i,t}$ signifies the trade-credit finance of firm i in year t . $ESG_RD_{i,t}$ indicates how different rating agencies rate ESG rating divergence for firm i across different years. $Controls_{i,t}$ states the set of control factors used in the study. To control unobservable

factors, we have used firm-fixed impacts $\lambda_{i,t}$ and year-fixed impacts λ_t , correspondingly. While $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ indicate random error term.

3.3 Variable definitions

3.3.1 Trade Credit Finance

Trade credit financing represents a company's internal liquidity in commerce¹. D'Mello and Toscano (2020) explored how trade credit financing emphasizes external credit and the factors influencing firms' short-term lending and borrowing. Studies by Fisman and Love (2003), Molina and Preve (2009), and Hill et al. (2012) demonstrate that advancements in trade credit financing can augment a company's operational and monetary outlook, boost stock returns and effectiveness, lower statistics gaps, and contribute to the development of the whole company. D'Mello and Toscano (2020) also found that trade credit financing significantly boosts a firm's value. Hence, following (Ge and Qiu, 2007; Chen and Ma, 2018), we have used the ratio of the sum of accounts payable (AP), notes payable (NP), and accounts receivable (AR) to total assets (TA) to measure the trade credit financing.

3.3.2 ESG Rating Divergence

The main factor in present research is ESG rating divergence (ESG_RD), which indicates inconsistencies in how every rating agency has its criteria to evaluate the same company. Previous studies have found that ESG rating disagreement using statistical dispersion of rating data (Christensen et al., 2022; Gibson et al., 2021; Kimbrough et al., 2022; Serafeim and Yoon, 2023). Precisely, ESG rating divergence is measured by deviation in a company's ESG ratings across different rating organizations within the same year. A more significant difference in standard deviation reflects higher divergence (Zhou et al., 2024). Following Avramov et al. (2022), we have measured ESG rating divergence using data from three prominent rating organizations: Bloomberg, Refinitive, and CNRDS. These databases are frequently cited in highest periodicals solving Chinese sustainability issues (Wang et al., 2023; Chen and Xie, 2022; Hossain et al., 2023; He et al., 2022; Li et al., 2023). Following Avramov et al. (2022), we initially developed three pairs of raters (i.e., two ESG ratings in each pair) from three rating agencies in this study. Subsequently, we calculate each pair's standard deviation and mean, resulting in three different standard deviations and means. Furthermore, we estimate an average of each pair's three calculated standard deviations. Finally, for the convenience of coefficient interpretation, we divide the ESG divergence (average standards deviation) proxy with the mean of all rating agencies pairs.

3.3.3 Mechanism test model

Customer concentration plays a vital part in identifying a company's trade credit choices. According to the literature, increased competition within an industry often benefits customers as firms become more inclined to offer favorable terms (Peng et al., 2019). Fabbri and Klapper (2016) further highlight that when customers possess significant bargaining power, they have greater freedom to choose where to purchase goods. In highly competitive markets, organizations are inclined to expand trade credit to their loyal and influential customers to maintain strong relationships (Fabbri & Menichini, 2009; Love et al., 2007).

To investigate the role of customer concentration (CUSTCC) on trade credit financing, this study suggests the following model:

$$CUSTCC_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 ESG_RD_{i,t} + \gamma Controls_{i,t} + \lambda_i + \lambda_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (5)$$

$$TRDCF_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 ESG_RD_{i,t} + \beta_2 CUSTCC_{i,t} + \gamma Controls_{i,t} + \lambda_i + \lambda_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (6)$$

In the mechanism model above, equations (5-6) represent the mediation variables (*CUSTCC*), while *Controls* refer to the control variables selected for the study. The coefficients β_1 and β_2 indicate the potential impact on trade credit financing, which can be either positive or negative. A negative coefficient

¹ "The article titled "World Bank urged to life trade credit finance" published by Financial Times on 11th November, 2008 affirm that trade credit "supports 90% of world merchandise trade" and furthermore Beck et al. (2008) conclude in their survey about firms in 48 countries that about 20% of firms' is financed by trade credit. Furthermore, also see Klapper et al. (2012)."

suggests that customer concentration is negatively related to TRDCF, whereas a positive coefficient would indicate the opposite effects.

3.3.4 Control Variables

We employed a standard set of control variables to alleviate the possible perplexing influences of other variables influencing trade credit financing. Consistent with prior literature (He & Jiang, 2019; Huang & Li, 2017; Li et al., 2023), we controlled for various firm-level features, comprising ESG mean, size, return on assets (ROA), leverage, cash flows from operating activities, fixed asset ratio, independent director ratio, age, and Big Four auditors. Detailed descriptions of these variables are presented in Appendix.

4. Empirical results.

4.1. Descriptive statistics

Summary indicators in [Table 1](#) reveal that the average ESG rating divergence (ESG_RD) of the present study is 0.556, while ESG_RD standard deviation is 0.260 indicating the existence of higher divergence in ESG ratings among distinct firms. Furthermore, the mean and standard deviation of ESG ratings are 0.428 and 0.073, respectively, indicating that the overall average performance of all listed firms in China needs improvement due to poor ESG performance. Notably, the control variable size has a higher mean value (22.290) compared to the return on asset (ROA), which has a lower mean value (i.e., 0.039). Similarly, standard deviation of size and firm age have higher values than other variables.

Table 1: Summary of descriptive statistics

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Min	P25	P50	P75	Max
TRDCF	12,586	0.263	0.159	0.019	0.136	0.235	0.362	0.796
ESG_RD	12,177	0.556	0.260	0.000	0.383	0.558	0.729	1.414
ESG_Mean	11,935	0.428	0.073	0.225	0.375	0.417	0.475	0.640
Size	12,588	22.290	1.243	19.960	21.369	22.098	23.005	26.443
Lev	12,590	0.414	0.194	0.061	0.257	0.408	0.554	0.912
ROA	12,589	0.039	0.063	-0.348	0.014	0.040	0.072	0.217
CFLOA	12,589	0.053	0.063	-0.155	0.015	0.051	0.090	0.255
PPE	12,589	0.401	0.170	0.058	0.269	0.393	0.526	0.829
Ind_Dr	12,167	0.380	0.087	0.142	0.333	0.375	0.428	0.625
Age	12,631	20.593	5.482	8.000	17.000	20.000	24.000	37.000
Big4_Aud	12,846	0.064	0.245	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.000

Note: The table presents the descriptive statistics of all variables. Where, N indicate number of observations.

4.2. Pearson correlation analysis (PCA) and Variance inflation factor (VIF).

[Table 2](#) denotes the pairwise correlation of explanatory, explained, and control variables. The variable of interest ESG rating divergence (ESG_RD) is statistically negatively correlated with trade credit financing (TRDCF). Furthermore, control variables size, leverage, and independent director ratio are positively correlated with ESG_RD. Conversely, ROA, CFLOA, firm age, and Big4 auditors are negatively correlated with the dependent variable. Furthermore, to scrutinize the multicollinearity issue, the variance inflation factor (VIF) has been estimated. Hence, [Table 2](#) indicates that the average value of VIF is 1.27, while the maximum VIF is 1.72, indicating that the VIF of all variables is less than standard 10 (Kennedy, 2008), indicating no multicollinearity issue in our model.

Table 2. Pairwise correlations and variance inflation factor

No	Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	VIF
1	TRDCF	1.000											
2	ESG_RD	-0.093*	1.000										1.17

3	ESG_Mean	0.092** *	0.001 *	1.000									1.0 4
4	Size	0.008* 0.344 ***	- 0.312 ***	0.002* 1.000									1.7 2
5	Lev	0.333 ***	- 0.312 ***	-0.085 ***	0.515 ***	1.000							1.6 9
6	ROA	-0.112 ***	0.122 ***	0.070 ***	- 0.015** *	- 0.351** *	1.00 0***						1.5 0
7	CFLOA	-0.180 ***	- 0.001 *	0.096** *	0.067 ***	-0.180 ***	0.43 6***	1.00 0					1.3 2
8	PPE	-0.335 ***	- 0.114 ***	0.140 ***	0.135** *	0.044** *	- 0.12 0***	0.11 0***	1.000				1.1 0
9	Ind_Dr	0.001* 0.018 ***	0.018 ***	0.030 ***	-0.060 ***	-0.040 ***	0.03 9***	0.02 3***	-0.030 ***	1.000			1.0 1
10	Age	-0.092 ***	- 0.192 ***	-0.014* 0.223 ***	0.223 ***	0.175 ***	- 0.07 4***	- 0.01 7***	0.074** *	- 0.041** *	1.00 0		1.0 7
11	Big4_Aud	-0.040 ***	- 0.065 ***	0.082 ***	0.279 ***	0.108 ***	0.03 7***	0.06 2***	0.023 ***	0.005* 0***	0.04 0	1.00 0	1.1 1
Mean VIF												1.2 7	

Note: This table indicate pairwise correlation of all variables and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) of all independent and control variables. Finally, ***, **, * represent significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% level respectively.

4.3. Baseline result estimation.

Based on the hypothesis (H1), Table 3 indicates the baseline regression result of ESG rating divergence (ESG_RD) and trade credit financing (TRDCF). Notably, the result of (M1) contains the ESG rating divergence coefficient and standard error -0.015 and 0.004, respectively, without control variables. However, the coefficient and standard error -0.010 and 0.004, respectively, in column (M2) after adding control variables, firm, and year fixed effect remain statistically significant at 5% level. The estimated coefficient of ESG rating divergence slightly changes from -0.015 to -0.010 after incorporating all control variables. The findings support our proposed hypothesis H1 that ESG rating divergence significantly negatively impacts trade credit financing.

Additionally, to capture the true performance of ESG rating performance on TRDCF, we have included the average of ESG performance as a control variable to check whether ESG rating divergence influences ESG rating performance. The estimated coefficient of the ESG rating mean in column (M2) is -0.025 with a standard error of 0.016, which is statistically negatively insignificant. The result demonstrate that in case of a notable deviation in ESG ratings from distinct rating organizations, the mean of ESG ratings may not correctly apprehend the firm's true ESG performance and its influence on trade credit financing. Hence, the result suggests that ESG rating divergence reduces actual ESG performance by enhancing information asymmetry.

In the panel fixed effect regression model, column (M2) results indicate that all controlled variables are statistically significant, except ESG mean, independent director ratio, and Big4 auditors. Furthermore, findings indicate that the estimated coefficient of firm size is negatively significant at a 1% significance level.

The said result is concurrent with the study of Wang and Yang. (2024) indicates that more prominent companies are less inclined towards trade credit financing. Similarly, CFLOA is negatively statistically significant, representing that companies decrease trade credit to customers when they earn lower profit from operating activities. Similarly, the projected coefficient of ROA is positively statistically significant evidence that when firms earn more profit compared to assets, then firms enhance account receivables time

deadline for customers, which consequently enhances TRDCF. Also, the effect of leverage on trade credit is positively significant at a 1% level, indicating that when companies have a greater ability to obtain loans from banks, it can facilitate trade credit to customers, consequently enhancing trade credit financing. In short, the estimated findings of all control variables of the present study are concurrent with the prior study (Petersen and Rajan, 1997).

Finally, we have individually examined the influence of rating divergence in the social (S_RD), environmental (E_RD), and governance (G_RD) pillars on trade credit financing. Following a homogenous ESG_RD proxy development methodology, we estimate divergence in individual E_RD, S_RD, and G_RD ratings by calculating the standard deviation among ratings delivered by distinct rating agencies. Table 3 indicates that the estimated coefficient of E_RD and S_RD are negatively significant at 5% and 1% level, respectively. On the contrary, G_RD estimated coefficient is positively statistically insignificant ($\beta = 0.0008, P > 0.10$). These findings propose that the inhibitory impact of ESG rating divergence on trade credit stems from the environmental and social rating supports. From the perspective of internal and external stakeholders, environmental and social dimensions are contemplated more closely related to a firm's sustainable development than governmental.

Table 3: Baseline regression results

Dependent Variable	Trade Credit Financing				
	(M1)	(M2)	(M3)	(M4)	(M5)
ESG_RD	-0.015*** (0.004)	-0.010** (0.004)	-	-	-
E_RD	-	-	-0.010** (0.005)	-	-
S_RD	-	-	-	-0.008*** (0.003)	-
G_RD	-	-	-	-	0.0008 (0.002)
ESG_Mean	-	-0.025 (0.016)	-0.040** (0.017)	-0.037** (0.016)	-0.024 (0.016)
Size	-	-0.023*** (0.005)	-0.022*** (0.005)	-0.022*** (0.005)	-0.023*** (0.005)
Lev	-	0.252*** (0.016)	0.253*** (0.016)	0.253*** (0.016)	0.253*** (0.016)
ROA	-	0.092*** (0.016)	0.093*** (0.016)	0.092*** (0.016)	0.093*** (0.016)
CFLOA	-	-0.057*** (0.013)	-0.057*** (0.013)	-0.056*** (0.013)	-0.057*** (0.013)
PPE	-	-0.125*** (0.015)	-0.125*** (0.015)	-0.125*** (0.015)	-0.125*** (0.015)
Ind_Dr	-	-0.114 (0.008)	-0.011 (0.008)	-0.011 (0.008)	-0.011 (0.008)
Age	-	0.003*** (0.000)	0.002*** (0.000)	0.002*** (0.000)	0.002*** (0.000)
Big4_Aud	-	0.004 (0.009)	0.005 (0.009)	0.004 (0.009)	0.004 (0.009)
Constant	0.270*** (0.002)	0.691*** (0.120)	0.699*** (0.121)	0.685*** (0.119)	0.684*** (0.121)
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Firm FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Adjusted R ²	0.005	0.121	0.121	0.121	0.120
Obs.	11,957	10,194	10,194	10,194	10,194

The results presented in columns (M1) and (M2) show the results of Panel regressions without and with control variables, respectively. Similarly, columns (M3), (M4), and (M5) exhibit the heterogeneity of Environmental, Social, and Governance rating divergence with firm and year-fixed effects, respectively. Finally, ***, **, and * show that the correlation is significant at 1%, 5%, and 10% respectively. However, the parenthesis contains the value of robust standard errors in all columns.

4.4. Robustness check.

4.4.1. Dependent variable adjustment

In the present study, we have used the variable substitution method to check the model's strength. First, the dependent factor TRDCF has been substituted with the sum of accounts payable and Notes payable divided by total assets (Luo et al., 2023). Column (M2) of Table 4 indicates that the projected coefficient of TRDCF is still negatively statistically significant at a 5% level ($\beta = -0.009, P < 0.05$), which further advocates our baseline result. Furthermore, the absolute value of the robust ESG_RD parameter is lower than the benchmark regression ($|\beta| = 0.009 < |\beta| = 0.010$).

4.4.2. Independent variable adjustment

Similarly, the key variable of interest (ESG_RD) has been replaced with an alternative proxy by calculating the standard deviation of all three rating agencies without creating a pair of two (Li et al., 2024). We reassess equation (1) after utilizing the alternative, independent variable measure. The results in M4 of Table 4 approve that the adverse statistically significant ($\beta = -0.008, P < 0.10$) effect of ESG_RD on TRDCF persists even after the independent variable has been replaced.

4.4.3. Time grouping

A robustness test for the time group was conducted after Broadstock et al. (2021) suggested that influence of ESG rating on stock return differs after and before the COVID-19 pandemic. During COVID-19, higher ESG performer stocks face substantial hazard in the worldwide fiscal crises, similar to the concept that supplier and customers may consider ESG performance as a signal for upcoming growth that ultimately reduces risk. Hence, the sample was classified after COVID-19 (2020-2022) and before COVID-19 (2018-2019), using 2020 as a limit. The regression result present in the last two columns of Table 4 indicates that the estimated coefficient ($\beta = -0.013, P < 0.05$) of ESG_RD has a more significant influence on TRDCF after 2020. The greater coefficient of ESG_RD after 2020 is due to the enhancement of awareness among suppliers and customers regarding the importance of ESG. In summary, Table 4 reveals consistent patterns, uniform significance, and the same average parameters across all six columns, confirming the reliability and robustness of the findings generated by the baseline model.

Table 4. Robustness tests- an alternative measure of trade credit financing, ESG rating divergence, and time grouping COVID-19 sampling year.

Variable	TRDCF		ESG Divergence		Time Grouping	
	(M1)	(M2)	(M3)	(M4)	Before 2020	After 2020
ESG_RD	-0.014*** (0.003)	-0.009** (0.004)	-0.009** (0.004)	-0.008* (0.004)	0.008 (0.006)	-0.013** (0.005)
ESG_Mean	-	-0.017 (0.014)	-	-0.038*** (0.015)	-0.023 (0.024)	-0.025 (0.018)
Size	-	-0.032*** (0.005)	-	-0.022*** (0.002)	-0.041*** (0.011)	-0.033*** (0.010)
Lev	-	0.182*** (0.014)	-	0.253*** (0.009)	0.227*** (0.025)	0.286*** (0.021)
ROA	-	0.078*** (0.014)	-	0.093*** (0.013)	0.049** (0.024)	0.101*** (0.024)
CFLOA	-	-0.082*** (0.012)	-	-0.057*** (0.011)	-0.026 (0.021)	-0.062*** (0.017)
PPE	-	-0.077*** (0.014)	-	-0.125** (0.009)	-0.103*** (0.023)	-0.109*** (0.018)
Ind_Dr	-	-0.012 (0.007)	-	-0.011 (0.007)	-0.019* (0.010)	-0.011 (0.011)
Age	-	0.002*** (0.000)	-	0.002*** (0.000)	0.008*** (0.001)	0.007*** (0.001)
Big4_Aud	-	0.007 (0.006)	-	0.005 (0.007)	0.010 (0.008)	0.005 (0.014)
Constant	0.234*** (0.002)	0.875*** (0.116)	0.266*** (0.002)	0.695*** (0.058)	0.987*** (0.236)	0.796*** (0.212)
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Firm FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Adjusted R ²	0.006	0.090	0.004	0.121	0.077	0.146
Obs.	11,952	10,201	11,957	10,194	4,062	6,132

The results present in columns M1 and M2 show the result of Panel regressions by analyzing the alternative proxy of the dependent variable, i.e., ((Account receivable + Account Payable)/Total assets). Similarly, columns M3 and M4 exhibit the findings of panel regressions utilizing the standard deviation of all rating agencies as independent variables. Additionally, columns M5 and M6 demonstrate the comparison of results before and after COVID-19 time period. Finally, ***, **, and * show that the correlation is significant at 1%, 5%, and 10% respectively. However, the parenthesis contains the value of robust standard errors in all columns.

4.5. Endogeneity test.

To mitigate the issue of endogeneity, we have utilized an instrumental variable approach in the present study. We have selected the concern level of research companies as an instrumental variable (IV), which is calculated by following Shen et al. (2023), i.e., total number of the research reports pursued and analyzed by research companies in each year. We have selected this IV due to the robust procedure of directing ESG ratings on firms. The rating agencies gather information about ESG factors from publically listed firms' annual reports, which they then organize and analyze. Hence, diverse rating agencies elucidate the information distinctively, leading to divergence in ESG (Berg et al., 2022). According to Roberts and Whited (2013), a good instrument variable (IV) should have an association with the exogenous variable but should not have any direct correlation with the dependent variable. Hence, consistent with this approach, the firm's level of focus is related to ESG rating deviation, but there is no direct association between the level of attention and TRDCF. The following model has been developed to estimate the endogeneity problem.

$$ESG_RD_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 IV_{i,t} + \Sigma controls_{i,t} + \lambda_i + \lambda_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \tag{7}$$

$$TRDCF_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \widehat{ESG_RD}_{i,t} + \Sigma controls_{i,t} + \lambda_i + \lambda_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \tag{8}$$

Model (7) investigates the impact of the instrument variable on the exogenous variable. Once the statistical significance of model (7) emphasizes the validity of interlink between the independent and IV, then model (8) will be employed to test the impact of IV on the independent and finally estimate the independent on the dependent variable. Column (M1) of Table 5 presents the first-stage regression result of an instrumental variable. The estimated coefficient of instrument variable (IV) is statistically significant at a 1% level ($\beta = -0.000, P < 0.01$). Furthermore, Anderson canon.corr.LM is 16.303 statistically significant at 1% level.

Similarly, Donald Wald F's statistic value is 16.467, surpassing the 16.38 threshold of the Stock –Yogo weak ID test. Hence, altogether, these results reject the null hypothesis (i.e., inadequate credentials and feeble contributory factors, respectively). Anderson-Rubin Wald's statistic P value is also significant at a 1% level, effectively rejecting the null hypothesis. Column (M2) indicates the regression result of IV; the projected coefficient of ESG_RD is statistically significant at a 1% level ($\beta = -0.782, P < 0.01$) at the second stage. The result settles that the negative effect of ESG rating divergence on TRDCF remains consistent with baseline results even when incorporating instrument variables.

Additionally, we have also used lagged (t-1) difference of dependent variable (TRDCF) in baseline equation in order to check the issue of simultaneity. The result of Table 5 (M3) exhibits that ESG rating divergence is still statistically significant at a 5% level ($\beta = -0.009, P < 0.05$) after incorporating TRDCF_{t-1} as an independent variable. This verdict reveals that there is no any issue of simultaneity in our baseline model. Hence, we may conclude that our baseline results are strongly robust.

Table 5: Endogeneity issue.

Variable	ESG_RD	TRDCF	TRDCF
	(M1)	(M2)	(M3)
Instrument variable (IV)	-0.000*** (0.000)	-	-
TRDCF _{t-1}	-	-	0.009* (0.005)

ESG_RD	-	-0.782*** (0.266)	-0.009** (0.004)
ESG_Mean	-0.064** (0.030)	-0.081*** (0.034)	-0.025* (0.013)
Size	-0.045*** (0.002)	-0.058*** (0.013)	-0.023*** (0.002)
Lev	-0.160*** (0.015)	0.280*** (0.045)	0.249*** (0.009)
ROA	0.172*** (0.046)	0.143** (0.059)	0.089*** (0.013)
CFLOA	-0.059 (0.039)	-0.182*** (0.049)	-0.059*** (0.011)
PPE	-0.068*** (0.013)	-0.398*** (0.023)	-0.122*** (0.009)
Ind_Dr	0.016 (0.024)	0.002 (0.026)	-0.010 (0.007)
Age	-0.005*** (0.000)	-0.006** (0.001)	0.003*** (0.000)
Big4_Aud	0.021** (0.009)	0.005 (0.012)	0.004 (0.007)
Constant	1.818*** (0.050)	2.232*** (0.509)	-0.689*** (0.058)
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Firm FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Adjusted R ²	0.069	0.476	0.120
Anderson canon.corr.LM statistics	16.303	(0.000)	-
Cragg-Donald Wald F statistics	16.467	(16.38)	-
Anderson-Rubin Wald statistics	27.74	(0.000)	-
Hansen J statistics	-	0.000	-
Obs.	10,194	10,194	10,108

The results presented in column M1 indicate the first stage result of the instrument variable. Meanwhile, M2 shows the panel regression of the estimated variable. In comparison, Column M3 demonstrates results of simultaneity issue by adding lagged effect of dependent variable. Meanwhile, the Hansen test shows the over-identification tests for variables. Finally, ***, **, and * show that the correlation is significant at 1%, 5%, and 10% respectively. However, the parenthesis contains the value of robust standard errors in all columns.

4.6. Mechanism analysis.

As previously discussed, signaling theory highlights that contribution to a firm's sustainable development is wholly associated with excellent answers to investors' expectations and demands, such as stockholders, suppliers, investors, and customers (Freeman and McVea, 2005). ESG performance is an irreplaceable unique asset and shows the stakeholder's detailed evaluation of the firm's prospects. Hence, this helps stakeholders, such as customers, to make purchase decisions. Jufri et al. (2022) evidence that a firm's perception of engagement in CSR/ESG significantly affects its recognition and consumer's purchase decision. Conversely, divergence in ESG rating significantly reduces reputation, consequently reducing customers' purchase decisions. Furthermore, prior studies evidence that ESG performance significantly improves the trade credit financing for the firm (Luo et al., 2023). In contrast, economic policy uncertainty similar to ESG rating divergence significantly reduces trade credit financing (D'Mello and Toscano, 2020).

In this study, we have utilized "revenue share of top 5 customers in percentage" as a proxy for customer concentration (Peng et al., 2019). The lower the CUSTCC, the more likely the customers reduce their purchases from firms due to divergence in ESG rating, consequently reducing trade credit financing (Account receivable) amount. The finding in Column M1 of Table 6 indicates that the coefficient of ESG rating divergence is statistically negative, with the customer concentration at a 10% significance level ($\beta = -0.011$, $P < 0.10$). This result is opposite to the findings of a prior study (Peng et al., 2019), which shows that customer concentration enhances informal financing (trade credit financing). Furthermore, we have investigate the impact of ESG_RD and CUSTCC on Trade credit financing without incorporating control variables. The results present in column M2 demonstrate that CUSTCC is positively statistically significant with TRDCF. Finally, the conclusions presented in column M3 of Table 6 reveal that ESG rating

divergence reduces TRDCF ($\beta = -0.009, P < 0.05$), while CUSTCC enhances TRDCF ($\beta = 0.029, P < 0.01$). In summary, this result supports our (H2) hypothesis that ESG rating divergence reduces trade credit financing by decreasing customer concentration.

Table 6: Mechanism analysis.

Variable	Customer Concentration (CUSTCC)	Trade Credit Financing (TRDCF)	
	(M1)	(M2)	(M3)
ESG_RD	-0.011* (0.006)	-0.015*** (0.004)	-0.009** (0.004)
CUSTCC	-	0.026* (0.014)	0.029*** (0.011)
ESG_Mean	-0.027 (0.021)	-	-0.020 (0.016)
Size	-0.025*** (0.004)	-	-0.022*** (0.005)
Lev	0.008 (0.014)	-	0.260*** (0.016)
ROA	0.108*** (0.020)	-	0.089*** (0.016)
CFLOA	0.027 (0.017)	-	-0.056*** (0.013)
PPE	-0.054*** (0.014)	-	-0.118*** (0.016)
Ind_Dr	0.018 (0.011)	-	-0.015* (0.008)
Age	0.004*** (0.009)	-	0.003*** (0.008)
Big4_Aud	0.027** (0.011)	-	0.005 (0.009)
Constant	0.832*** (0.087)	-	0.663*** (0.121)
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Firm FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Adjusted R ²	0.015	0.007	0.129
Obs.	10,096	11,638	9,963

The results presented in columns (M1) show the impact of ESG divergence on customer concentration. However, columns (M2) and (M3) represent the influence of CUSTCC on trade credit financing without and with control variables, respectively. Finally, ***, **, and * show that the correlation is significant at 1%, 5%, and 10% respectively. However, the parenthesis contains the value of robust standard errors in all columns.

4.7. Heterogeneity test.

In this study, we have estimated heterogeneity analysis from the perspective of carbon emission and willingness of disclosure to identify the in-depth impact of ESG rating divergence on TRDCF. As stipulated in the given deliberations, firms with distinct carbon emission concentrations may reveal different sensitivities to ESG rating divergence. Higher carbon emission firms bear strict social responsibilities and environmental provocations from stakeholders, customers, suppliers, and investors due to the green transformation of the firm's resource input and production methodology. Hence, high carbon-emitting firms may be more sensitive compared to low carbon-emitting firms from the realm of divergence in ESG rating. Second, ESG information disclosure is one of the vital factors impacting ESG rating divergence. Therefore, we develop a group of companies based on organizations' willingness to disclose information to examine whether information disclosure impacts the ESG rating deviation process on trade credit financing.

4.7.1. Group based on carbon intensity

In order to investigate the in-depth analysis, following criteria developed by the Ministry of Ecology and Environment 2021, we have categorized the group of firms into two distinct clusters: High and low-carbon emission firms. In detail, firms falling under the classification of chemical, electric power, building material, petrochemical, paper making, steels, non-ferrous metal, and aviation are considered high carbon emission

firms, while the rest are classified as low carbon emission firms. Table 7 presents the regression results of the sub-groups mentioned above in the (M1) and (M2) columns. The result indicates that the estimated coefficient of high carbon firms is negatively significant at a 10% level ($\beta = -0.019, P < 0.10$). However, the estimated coefficient of low carbon firms is negatively statistically insignificant at a 10% level ($\beta = -0.007, P > 0.10$). Hence, this reveals that the degree of carbon emission impacts the association among ESG rating divergence and TRDCF. The rationale for this phenomenon is that suppliers and customers strictly focus on high-carbon companies, and as ESG rating divergence increases, uncertainty among stakeholders' increases, leading to information asymmetry mismatch and decreased trade credit financing.

4.7.2. Group based on information disclosure willingness

Similarly, we have classified sub-samples into two sets based on firms' proactive disclosure of ESG activity reports. We assigned value one to firms that actively disclose ESG responsibilities. Conversely, we assigned value zero to firms that non-voluntarily disclose ESG reports. Columns (M3) and (M4) of Table 7 show the results of firms engaging in voluntary and non-voluntary disclosure of ESG reports, respectively. The result indicates that for firms engaging in disclosure reports, the effect of ESG rating deviation has a significant influence on trade credit financing ($\beta = -0.011, P < 0.10$), while for firms those not engaging in disclosure reports, the influence of divergence in ESG rating is negatively insignificant on trade credit financing ($\beta = -0.005, P > 0.10$). These findings support the evidence of prior study Christensen et al. (2022), which advocate that higher disclosure of statistics reports used by different rating agencies based on idiosyncratic assessment leads to higher ESG divergence. However, higher disclosure of ESG reports provides more data to investors, customers, and suppliers that can create easiness for stakeholders to make decisions; it simultaneously reveals challenges.

Table 7: Heterogeneity analysis.

Variable	High Carbon Firms (M1)	Low Carbon Firms (M2)	Voluntary disclosure (M3)	Non-voluntary disclosure (M4)
ESG_RD	-0.019* (0.010)	-0.007 (0.005)	-0.011* (0.006)	-0.005 (0.008)
ESG_Mean	-0.020 (0.034)	-0.039 (0.018)	-0.034 (0.021)	-0.024 (0.026)
Size	-0.009 (0.014)	-0.027*** (0.006)	-0.029*** (0.006)	-0.008 (0.012)
Lev	0.197*** (0.043)	0.258*** (0.018)	0.248*** (0.018)	0.250*** (0.035)
ROA	0.058 (0.036)	0.094*** (0.017)	0.087*** (0.018)	0.119*** (0.033)
CFLOA	-0.011 (0.029)	-0.056*** (0.015)	-0.064*** (0.016)	-0.015 (0.026)
PPE	-0.079** (0.036)	-0.127*** (0.017)	-0.127*** (0.018)	-0.104*** (0.033)
Ind_Dr	0.009 (0.018)	-0.014 (0.009)	-0.015 (0.009)	-0.005 (0.015)
Age	0.004** (0.002)	0.002** (0.000)	0.003*** (0.001)	0.001 (0.001)
Big4_Aud	-0.031** (0.015)	0.007 (0.010)	0.007 (0.012)	-0.002 (0.012)
Constant	0.325 (0.286)	0.792*** (0.137)	0.836*** (0.132)	0.358 (0.271)
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Firm FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Adjusted R ²	0.106	0.123	0.126	0.097
Obs.	1,497	8,697	7,320	2,874

The results presented in columns (M1) and (M2) show the cross-sectional heterogeneity of high and low-carbon emission firms, respectively. Similarly, columns (M3) and (M4) exhibit the heterogeneity of high ESG disclosure and low ESG disclosure with firm and year-fixed effects, respectively. Finally, ***, **, and * show that the correlation is significant at 1%, 5%, and 10% respectively. However, the parenthesis contains the value of robust standard errors in all columns.

4.8. Cross-sectional test

4.8.1. Firm transparency

In the earlier results, we conclude that ESG rating divergence reduces TRDCF by enhancing information asymmetry between suppliers, customers, and firms. Therefore, corporations with distinct information transparency levels may influence trade credit financing differently. If ESG divergence increases statistics irregularity and decreases information transparency, ESG rating divergence's influence on TRDCF will be more substantial in firms with lower facts transparency. Hence, in the present study following Francis and Yu. (2009), we used firms audited by Big4 as a proxy to measure information transparency. Notably, Big 4 audit corporations have a significant audit quality compared to others, which can mitigate information asymmetry by improving information transparency. Therefore, we have classified firms into lower information transparency (not audited by Big4 auditor) and higher information transparency (audited by Big4 auditor). The estimated results of information transparency heterogeneity are presented in columns (M1) and (M2) of Table 8. The result reveals that the estimated coefficient of ESG rating divergence is negatively statistically significant ($\beta = -0.011, P < 0.05$) in sub-sample with lower transparency, while insignificant ($\beta = -0.006, P > 0.10$) in firms with higher transparency. This result advocates that ESG rating divergence further declines TRDCF for firms with lower information transparency.

4.8.2. Cost of Debt.

The cost of debt (CoD) is one of the key factors suppliers consider before providing a credit deadline. Suppliers use this to evaluate whether firms can repay their liabilities as promised. Additionally, future operational efficiency acts as insurance for the ability of firms to repay liabilities. Hence, establishing a debt contract with the creditor's future operational growth is vital for suppliers' decision-making. Luo et al. (2023) evidence that ESG performance increases TRDCF for organizations with higher debt costs. In contrast, we posit that ESG rating divergence further declines trade credit financing for group of firms with significant debt costs. Hence, based on the above statement, we have calculated the ratio of interest expenses to total debt as a proxy to estimate CoD (Pitman and Fortin, 2004). We have divided the sample on the basis of the median value of the cost of debt each year. The calculated coefficient of ESG rating dispersion for firms with higher cost of debt presented in column (M3) of Table 8 is negatively significant at a 1% level ($\beta = -0.020, P < 0.01$). In contrast, the estimated coefficient of the lower cost of debt group of firms is negatively insignificant ($\beta = -0.003, P > 0.10$). Therefore, this result concludes that ESG rating divergence deteriorate firms efficiency, which impedes firms from accessing more trade credit financing.

Table 8: Cross-sectional heterogeneity analysis.

Variable	Big4_Audit (M1)	No Big4_Audit (M2)	Higher CoD (M3)	Lower CoD (M4)
ESG_RD	-0.006 (0.012)	-0.011** (0.004)	-0.020*** (0.007)	-0.003 (0.006)
ESG_Mean	-0.070 (0.047)	-0.020 (0.017)	-0.030 (0.026)	-0.015 (0.020)
Size	-0.020 (0.023)	-0.023*** (0.006)	-0.023*** (0.007)	-0.030*** (0.009)
Lev	0.197*** (0.046)	0.255*** (0.016)	0.278*** (0.024)	0.237*** (0.023)
ROA	0.098 (0.066)	0.091*** (0.016)	0.082*** (0.024)	0.109*** (0.023)
CFLOA	-0.130* (0.066)	-0.052*** (0.013)	-0.046** (0.020)	-0.086*** (0.019)
PPE	-0.123 (0.042)	-0.123*** (0.016)	-0.165*** (0.028)	-0.066*** (0.019)
Ind_Dr	-0.011 (0.021)	-0.010 (0.008)	-0.019 (0.013)	-0.002 (0.010)
Age	0.006*** (0.002)	0.002*** (0.0008)	0.002** (0.001)	0.003*** (0.001)
Big4_Aud	-	-	0.017 (0.015)	-0.003 (0.012)

Constant	0.589	(0.514)	0.692*** (0.123)	0.757*** (0.164)	0.770*** (0.184)
Year FE	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Firm FE	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Adjusted R ²	0.107		0.122	0.143	0.110
Obs.	571		9,623	4,961	5,233

The results presented in columns (M1) and (M2) show the cross-sectional heterogeneity of firms audited by Big4 auditors and Not-Big4 auditors, respectively. Similarly, columns (M3) and (M4) exhibit the heterogeneity of firms with higher cost of debt vs lower cost of debt with firm and year-fixed effect, respectively. Finally, ***, **, and * show that the correlation is significant at 1%, 5%, and 10% respectively. However, the parenthesis contains the value of robust standard errors in all columns.

5. Conclusions

In recent years, trade credit financing has been vital for corporate growth (Tingbani et al., 2024). Several variables like firm characteristics, management characteristic, internal control, financial environment, economic conditions, and monetary policy influence trade credit financing. Prior studies have evidence that ESG performance augments TRDCF. In contrast, economic policy uncertainty (EPU) inhibits TRDCF. Similar to EPU, investigating the impact of ESG rating divergence on TRDCF, we have employed data about all A share publically listed non-financial Chinese firms listed on the Shenzhen and Shanghai stock exchanges from 2018-2022.

Furthermore, we have also examined the mechanism through which ESG rating divergence inhibits trade credit financing. Following are the key findings of the present study. First, we uncover that a 1% enhance in divergence of ESG rating significantly declines 0.010% of TRDCF. The result of the present study stands true after employing a series of robustness tests like instrumental variable, lagged difference, and substitution of independent and dependent variables.

Second, customer concentration plays a significant mediating part in the process of ESG rating discrepancy on TRDCF. Third, the present study evidences that there is a presence of heterogeneity in the influence of ESG rating disagreement on trade credit financing. Firms that exaggerates ESG reports, high carbon firms, low transparency firms, and firms with higher debt costs experience more pronounced detrimental influences on trade credit financing due to divergence in ESG rating. Finally, we conclude that the detrimental impact of ESG rating divergence on TRDCF stems from environmental and social rating divergence pillars rather than the governance pillar.

6. Policy implications

The conclusion of this study has several implications for academics, companies, rating agencies, regulators, and policymakers as they increasingly pay attention to the ESG disclosure factors and their value relevance to investors, customers, suppliers, and other stakeholders. First, to enhance the reliability and accuracy of the ESG rating and reduce the dispersion in ESG rating caused by data evaluation methodology, the Sustainability Accounting Standards Board (SASB) and International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) should establish proper global accounting standards for mitigating the divergence in ESG rating in diverse countries. Second, incentives such as providing tax breaks, lowering CoD, and supplementary motivations should be introduced to inspire Chinese listed firms to enthusiastically disclose more comprehensive ESG information. Hence, this will make it easy for rating agencies to understand the firm's true ESG performance, causing decreased ESG rating divergence. Additionally, the government can further enhance information disclosure by granting special funds on account of detailed ESG information. Third, firms and governments altogether encourage ethos and a sustainable development attitude. Firms and governments can achieve this by training and educating customers and suppliers to evaluate and understand ESG performance better, which affects corporate growth and trade credit financing. Fourth, ESG rating agencies should reinforce their internal system by employing talented team members with specialized capabilities and knowledge relevant to ESG factors. This endeavor is to increase the authenticity and accuracy of evaluating ESG scores, reducing ESG rating divergence. Fifthly, firms should also enhance information transparency because it reduces information asymmetry, reducing divergence in ESG rating.

7. Limitations

Following are the limitations of the present study that require attention. First, the mediating role of supplier concentration may also significantly impact on the divergence ESG rating and TRDCF. Hence, future studies can comprehensively capture this aspect. Second, we focus on only publicly listed firms in China due to data accessibility constraints. Hence, this center may inhibit the generalizability of present findings in private or SME firms. Furthermore, future studies can investigate the influence of EGS rating divergence on private firms. Future endeavors can get in-depth knowledge by contemplating longitudinal studies, extending the sampling period, using mixed methodologies, case studies, or interviews.

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Appendix: Table A. Variable definitions

Variable	Parameters	Character	Definition	Source
Dependent				
	Trade Credit Financing	TRDCF _{it}	A firm's (Account receivable + Account payable + Note payable)/Total Assets.	CSMAR
Independent				
	Environmental, Social, and Governance Rating Divergence	EGS_RD _{it}	The standard deviation of ESG ratings assigned by different rating agencies for the same firm.	Bloomberg, Refinitive, CNRDS
	Environmental Rating Divergence	E_RD _{it}	The standard deviation of Environmental ratings assigned by different rating agencies for the same firm.	Bloomberg, Refinitive, CNRDS
	Social Rating Divergence	S_RD _{it}	The standard deviation of Social ratings assigned by different rating agencies for the same firm.	Bloomberg, Refinitive, CNRDS
	Governance Rating Divergence	G_RD _{it}	The standard deviation of Governance ratings assigned by different rating agencies for the same firm.	Bloomberg, Refinitive, CNRDS
Mediator				
	Customer Concentration	CUSTCC _{it}	Revenue share of the top 5 Customers (%).	CNRDS
Control				
	ESG Average	ESG_Mean	Average of ESG score of all three rating agencies.	Bloomberg, Refinitive, CNRDS
	Size	Size _{it}	Natural logarithm of total asset.	CSMAR
	Leverage	Lev _{it}	The ratio of total liabilities to total assets.	CSMAR
	Return on Asset	ROA _{it}	The ratio of Net income to total assets.	CSMAR
	Cash Flow From Operating Activities	CFLOA _{it}	Ratio of cash flow from operating activities by total assets.	CSMAR
	Property Plant and Equipment	PPE _{it}	The ratio of fixed assets to total assets.	CSMAR
	Independent Directors	Ind_dr _{it}	The ratio of independent directors to total number of members.	CSMAR
	Firm Age	Age _{it}	Natural logarithm of years since firms have been established.	CSMAR
	Big4 Auditors	Big4_Aud _{it}	The dummy variable is assigned a value of 1 if a Big 4 audit firm audits a firm; otherwise, 0.	CSMAR

Note: Proxies are developed based on a literature review.

Abbreviations:

ESG = Environmental, Social, Governance

SSE = Shanghai Stock Exchange

SZSE = Shenzhen Stock Exchange

CNRDS = Chinese Research Data Services

TRDCF = Trade Credit Finance

ESG_RD = ESG Rating Divergence

E_RD = Environmental Rating Divergence

S_RD = Social Rating Divergence

G_RD = Governance Rating Divergence

CUSTCC = Customer Concentration

Lev = Leverage

ROA = Return on Assets

CFLOA = Cash Flow from Operating Activities

PPE = Property Plant and Equipment

Ind_Dr = Independent Director Ratio